

Influence of Land Use on Spatio-Temporal Variation in Soil Moisture in a Sahel Area of North East Nigeria

Ibraheem Alhassan¹

*1 - Department of Agronomy, Federal University, Gashua,
PMB 1005 Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria*

Corresponding Author: Ibraheem Alhassan

e-mail: ialhassand@gmail.com

Received: 31 December 2023

Accepted: 7 April 2024

Abstract

Soil moisture plays a great role in physical, chemical and biological activities in the soils. A research was conducted to determine the soil moisture contents across three land use types (grassland (GL), forested area (FR) and cultivated land (CL)) over a period of three months during rainy season in Federal University Gashua, North East of Nigeria. Soil samples were taken from each land use type using soil auger at 0-15 and 15-30cm depths for physico-chemical properties analysis, while core samples were taken fortnightly and after every rainy event for gravimetric soil moisture content (SMC) and bulk density determination. Results showed that the soils across the land uses are sandy loam in texture, high bulk density at GL and CL ($>1.80\text{g cm}^{-3}$) and moderate in FR (1.45g cm^{-3}), very low organic matter content and neutral in pH value. Significantly high SMC was recorded in FR and lower in GL with a high coefficient of variation (43%). Temporally, the SMC varied moderately (35% coefficient of variation) with significant increase after every rainfall event. The high bulk density and very low water retention capacity of the soils of the study area can be enhanced by conservation farming practices and constant addition of organic matter.

Keywords: Gashua, moisture, north east, savanna, soil.

Introduction

Physical, chemical, and biological processes of the soil system are usually influenced by soil moisture content (Brevik et al., 2015). Water contained in the soil is called soil moisture, its presence and movement are key variables for different applications in the fields of agriculture and vegetation growth monitoring, climate system, hydrology and stream flow prediction (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2014). Understanding soil water variations under different land use types is critical for agricultural water management and land erosion control (Gao and Shao, 2012; Ziadat and Taimeh, 2013).

Soil moisture is one of the key factors limiting the growth of plants most especially in the arid and semi-arid environment where the crop water requirements in most cases are

beyond the water supply, but even in the humid environment where poor rainfall distribution and water management results in occasional water stresses (Musa and Adeoye, 2010).

Land use change was found also to contribute to the variability of soil moisture, leading to soil deterioration, agricultural productivity decline and land degradation (Biro et al., 2013; Leh et al., 2013; Parras-Alcántara and Lozano-García, 2014). Evaluation of the temporal and spatial variation of soil moisture in numerous land uses is important for vegetation restoration and watershed management (Li et al., 2018). The soil internal factors affecting the spatial and temporal changes of soil moisture were mainly roots, soil texture, and soil organic carbon, and reported that soil clay content was the major factor affecting the spatial distribution of soil water on a semi-arid land (Gao and Shao, 2012). The temporal variation in soil moisture was also driven by meteorological properties like seasonal changes in temperature and evapotranspiration (Jia et al., 2017). In arid and semi-arid regions, the most important limiting factor to sustainable crop production is soil moisture. This valuable resource for sustainable agriculture must be monitored, conserved and managed well. Knowledge of the spatial and temporal distribution of soil moisture and the impact of land use types on its availability is indispensable for correct management strategies. In some tropical regions the availability of reliable data for water retention in respect to soil type, texture and organic matter content is low, it therefore became desirable to analyze the soil so as to estimate its water retention capacity through moisture content determination within the selected land uses for sustainable water management. The study was conducted to determine the soil moisture variation on the selected land use types in Gashua, Yobe State, North East, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at Federal University Gashua, Bade Local Government Area of Yobe State, Nigeria. Bade LGA is located between longitudes $12^{\circ} 30'$ and $12^{\circ} 65'N$ and latitudes $10^{\circ} 35'$ and $11^{\circ} 15'E$ (Figure 1). The area is situated in the Sahel savanna agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. It has an area of 809.661 km² with a population of 139,804. The most important vegetation type is that of the Sahel savannah, which consists mostly of open thorny savannah with short trees and grasses (Alhassan et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Location map of the study area

Geology and soils of the study area

The area is located within the Chad basin, lithological description consist of continental depositions, which was deposited unconformable over the Precambrian crystalline basement rock (Agada et al., 2020). The soils of Bade LGA showed a dominance of sand particles and most of them belong to the textural class of sandy loam with very low level of most of the essential nutrients (Alhassan et al., 2018).

Climate of the study area

The climate is characterized by high atmospheric temperature and low seasonal rainfall. The mean minimum temperature ranges between 10-12°C usually in December/January, while the mean maximum is about 35-42°C mostly in March to May. The annual average rainfall is about 300-450 mm per annum and is unimodal and lasts from July to October while the dry season starts from late October to May (Alhassan et al., 2020).

Soil sampling techniques

The sampled land use type's locations and coordinates were cultivated land (11°00'90"N, 12°52'57"E), forested area (11°00'95"N, 12°54'56"E) and grass land (11°00'75"N, 12°53'11"E). Three soil samples collected using soil auger from each of the selected land use types at 0-15 and 15-30 cm depths at random. A total of 18 soil samples were then collected from the three land use types. Composite samples were made for each sampling depth thus, arriving at six composite samples which were then package separately in polythene bags according to depth and site for processing and laboratory analysis.

Soil analysis

The samples were air-dried separately, ground using a pestle and mortar, and sieved through a 2 mm sieve for particle size analyses, pH, EC, organic matter and other chemical properties. Particle size distribution was determined by hydrometer method. pH (in water) was determined potentiometrically using pH meter in a 1:2.5 soil: water ratio. Electrical conductivity (EC) was determined from soluble salts in an extracted solution of 1:2.5 soil: water ratio using electric conductivity meter. Organic carbon (OC) was determined by Walkley-Black dichromate wet oxidation method, percent of OM was obtained by multiplying percent soil OC by a factor of 1.724. Total nitrogen content of the soil was analyzed by micro-Kjeldahl method. Exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) were extracted with 1.0M NH₄OAc solution buffered at pH 7.0. Calcium and Magnesium in the filtrate were determined with an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, while K and Na with Flame Photometer. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by neutral (pH 7.0) NH₄OAc saturation method. Available phosphorus (AP) was determined using after the extraction of the soil samples with 0.5M sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) following the Olsen extraction method (Estefan et al., 2013).

Determination of soil moisture, soil bulk density and soil porosity

Soil samples for soil moisture determination were taken also at 0-15cm and 15-30cm depths using core sampler. Samples were taken fortnightly and two days after every rain to determine the temporal trend and effect of rainfall respectively on soil moisture content under

the selected land use types. Samples were taken from 8th August to 31st October, 2021. The samples were then weighed for moist weight (ww) and placed in an Oven to dry at a temperature of 105°C for 24 hours. The dried samples were then weighed to obtain the dry weight (wd). It is then obtained using the expression in Hillel (2014):

$$SMC (\%) = \frac{ww (g) - wd (g)}{wd (g)} \times 100$$

(Eq.1)

Where: SMC (%) = soil moisture content in percentage, ww = weight of wet soil (g), wd = weight of dry soil (g).

Bulk density was determined on individual samples by dividing the oven-dry weight of the sample by the volume of the soil probe at the respective depth (Reeuwijk, 1992).

$$\text{Bulk density } (\rho_b) = \frac{M_s}{V_t}$$

(Eq.2)

Where: M_s = is the soil oven- dried mass, V_t = volume of the soil core sampler.

Porosity was determined using equation as (one minus the solid volume fraction of a sample (the bulk and particle densities). The ratio of the bulk density (D_b), to the particle density (P_p), describes the fraction of the total volume occupied by solids (Hao et al., 2008).

$$TP (\%) = [1 - \left(\frac{\rho_b}{\rho_s}\right)] \times 100$$

(Eq.3)

Where; TP = total porosity, ρ_b = bulk density, ρ_s = particle density (average value of 2.65 g cm⁻³ is used as particle density).

Data analysis

Statistical analyses performed to test the influence of soil moisture on different land use using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance), and comparisons of the difference between mean water content in different land uses were separated by least significant difference (LSD) method using STAR statistical package (STAR, 2013).

Results and Discussion

Effect of land use types on soil physical properties

The soil particle size distribution (PSD) showed that the sand ($p=0.08$) and silt ($p=0.21$) fractions did not significantly differ among land use types (Table 1) and clay ($p=0.04$) was significant different with the land use. The highest overall clay content was recorded under forest land (16.00%) and the lowest in the grass land (13.00%). High clay content in the forested area may be due to the nature of the erosional sediments deposited. The soils of the study area is sandy loam in texture. Similarly, Shehu *et al.* (2015) reported that most of the soils in savanna zone of northern Nigeria had sandy loam texture.

Soil bulk density (BD) ($p=0.0001$) found to be significantly different with the land uses. The soil bulk density was found to be very high in GL with the mean value of 1.85g cm⁻³ which is at par with CL (1.83g cm⁻³) and lower bulk density was recorded in FR with the mean value (1.35g cm⁻³). The lower bulk density found in FR could be due to high organic matter content as the area is covered with trees and grasses, while very high BD in GL and CL it may be due to low organic matter content. Result in GL and CL is very high and could

restrict root penetration as reported in Alhassan *et al.* (2018) that normal range of bulk density for clay is 0.90 to 1.40 g cm⁻³ and a normal range for sand is 1.40 to 1.90 g cm⁻³ with potential root restriction occurring at > 1.40 g cm⁻³ for clay and > 1.60 g cm⁻³ for sand, he also reported mean bulk density value (1.63 g cm⁻³) for soils of Bade LGA in Yobe State, Nigeria. The mean bulk densities recorded are relatively high for crop growth, a desirable bulk density for the soil should be < 1.5 g cm⁻³ and bulk densities greater than 1.6 g cm⁻³ usually restrict root growth (Brady and Weil, 2013)

Porosity ($p=0.0001$) significantly differs within the land use types, the lowest porosity was recorded in GL 30.19% and CL 30.82% and the highest porosity was found in FR 49.06%. Higher porosity found in FR may be due to the high organic matter in the land use, low bulk density and less disturbance. The low porosity recorded in GL and CL it may be due to high bulk density and intensive farming and grazing activities on these lands. This corroborates the work of Abdullah et al. (2018).

Table 1. Effect of Land Use on Soil Physical Properties

Land use	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Textural Class	BD (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)
GL	61.00	26.00	13.00b	SL	1.85a	30.19b
CL	60.00	25.50	14.50ab	SL	1.83a	30.82b
FR	55.50	28.50	16.00a	SL	1.45b	49.06a
SE	2.27	1.67	0.97		0.0186	0.7038
Pr(>F)	0.08	0.21	0.04		0.0000	0.0000
CV%	5.46	8.84	9.48		6.38	11.02

SL = Sandy Loam/ BD=Bulk density/GL=Grass Land/ CL= Cultivated Land/ FR=Forested Area/ SE=Standard Error/ CV=Coefficient of Variance

Effect of land use on soil chemical properties

The results showed that pH ($p=0.19$), EC ($p=0.42$), OC ($p = 0.92$), Na⁺ ($p=0.87$), available phosphorus (AP) ($p=0.18$) where not significantly different with the land use types, while OM ($p= 0.01$), CEC (0.00), N ($p= 0.02$), Mg⁺⁺ ($p= 0.01$), Ca⁺⁺ ($p= 0.00$) and K⁺, ($p=0.02$) concentrations where significantly different within the land uses (Table 2).

The soil pH showed little variability across the land uses with a mean value of 6.98 in GL, 6.76 in CL and 7.10 in FR, the soils are then categorized as neutral as the pH range between 6.51 and 7.5 (QldGov, 2013). The pH values of 6.5 to 7.5 is considered ideal for crop production, therefore, the soil pH values of the study area is considered good for crop production and will not require any amendment (Estefan et al., 2013).

Organic carbon (OC) was not significantly different with the land use types ($p=0.92$). The mean OC recorded are 0.90 g/kg in grass land, 0.93 g/kg in cultivated land and 0.87 g/kg in forested area. The OC content within the soils were considered low according to Esu (1991) rating (<10 g/kg) and is in agreement with Shehu et al. (2018) who reported less than 0.8% OC within the top 30 cm in Southern Guinea Savanna of North Central Nigeria. The soil OC with (CV=17.11%) is moderately varied within the land uses. Bationo and Buerkert (2001) reported 0.4% as a mean concentration of organic carbon within the topsoil of an area in

Sudan zone and 0.2% for the Sahel zone and further opined that the soils in the Sudano-Sahelian zone are inherently low in OC.

Soil organic matter OM ($p=0.01$), were significantly different within the land uses, 0.53g/kg was recorded in grass land, 0.55 g/kg in cultivated land and 0.41 g/kg in forested land. All were found to be very low within the land use types which could be attributed to low vegetative cover as a result of low rainfall that characterizes Sahel savanna areas like Gashua. The study area is characterized by low precipitation and high temperature, this may also contribute to low level of OM as reported to have effect on low of organic matter accumulation (Hamza and Anderson, 2010). Similarly the low organic matter content of the soils in all areas could be attributed to factors such as continuous cultivation, frequent burning of farm residues commonly carried out by farmers in the area which tends to destroy much of the organic materials that could have been added to the soil (Sharu et al., 2013).

Available phosphorus ($p=0.18$) was found to be not significant within the land uses, 8.75mg kg⁻¹ was recorded in grass land, 8.31mg kg⁻¹ in cultivated land and 9.34 mg kg⁻¹ in forested area also generally rated low (<10 mg/kg) according to Esu (1991). This result falls within the range presented by Alhassan et al. (2020) that available P in the soils of Bade ranged from 7.31- 11.37 mg kg⁻¹. Total nitrogen ($p=0.02$) is significantly different within the land use types. The mean value of 0.04 g/kg was recorded in grass land, 0.08 g/kg in cultivated land and 0.07 g/kg in forested area, indicating overall low level of N according Esu (1991) ratings. The low TN observed in the study area might be due to continues cultivation by farmers over the years and crop removal by uptake.

The CEC ($p=0.00$) was significantly different within the land uses. The mean value of 7.32 cmol(+)/kg was recorded in grass land, 8.11 cmol(+)/kg in cultivated land and 7.74 cmol(+)/kg recorded under forested area. The CEC content is relatively medium as shown that the CEC content between 6 - 12 cmol(+)/kg is median reported by Esu (1991). As the soils were generally low in organic carbon contents, it is probable that the medium CEC obtained could be as a result of the presence of high activity clays and high content of basic cations from parent materials.

The Ca⁺⁺ content ($p=0.01$) was significantly different within the land uses. The mean value recorded in grass land was 6.83 cmol(+)/kg, in cultivated land 6.24 cmol(+)/kg and in forested area 6.11 cmol(+)/kg. The calcium concentration was found to be very high within the land uses. The Mg⁺⁺ contents ($p=0.01$) were found to be significantly different within the land use 1.11 cmol(+)/kg was recorded in grass land, 1.68 cmol(+)/kg in cultivated land and forested area 1.44 cmol(+)/kg. The high level of Mg⁺⁺ might be due to the dominance of Mg bearing minerals in the area. The K⁺ concentration ($p=0.00$) was significantly different within the land use types. Moderately K⁺ content was recorded in grass land (0.24 cmol(+)/kg) and forested area (0.22 cmol(+)/kg) and significantly higher concentration of K⁺ was recorded in cultivated land with the mean value 1.13cmol(+)/kg.

The Na⁺ content of the soil ($p=0.87$) was not significantly different within the land use. Na⁺ recorded within grass land has a mean value 0.15 cmol(+)/kg, while in the cultivated land and forested area were 0.14 cmol(+)/kg each. High soil Na⁺ (>0.3) was also reported by Amalu (1997). The electric conductivity (EC) ($p=0.42$) is not significant different within the land uses. The mean value recorded in grass land was 0.15 (ds/m), 0.10 (ds/m) in cultivated land and 0.15 (ds/m) in forested area.

Table 2. Effect of Land use on Soil Chemical Properties

Land use	pH	EC	OC	OM	CEC	TN	Mg ⁺⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	AP
		(ds/m)	g/kg	g/kg	cmol(+)/kg	g/kg	cmol(+)/kg	cmol(+)/kg	cmol(+)/kg	cmol(+)/kg	mg/kg
GL	6.98	0.15	0.9	0.53a	7.32c	0.04b	1.11c	6.83a	0.24b	0.15	8.75
CL	6.76	0.1	0.89	0.41b	8.11a	0.08a	1.44b	6.11b	1.13a	0.14	8.31
FR	7.1	0.14	0.93	0.55a	7.74b	0.07a	1.68a	6.24b	0.22b	0.14	9.34
SE	0.17	0.02	0.11	0.03	0.05	0.01	0.09	0.18	0.03	0.02	0.51
Pr(>f)	0.19	0.42	0.92	0.01	0	0.02	0.01	0.01	0	0.87	0.18
CV%	3.55	32	17.11	9.79	0.99	26.69	9.87	4.08	10.61	2.05	8.17

GL=Grass Land/ CL= Cultivated Land/ FR=Forested Area/ SE=Standard Error/ CV=Coefficient of Variance

Effect of land uses on soil moisture content

The mean soil moisture content in three land uses are shown in Table 3. The soil moisture content within the land uses were highly significantly different ($p = 0.002$). In general, higher mean moisture content (13.53%) was recorded in forested area (FR) which is at par with 13.01% recorded under cultivated land (CL), while the minimum (10.39%) was found in grassland (GL). The high moisture content recorded under forested area may be due to high organic matter content through shade provided by the trees canopies which may reduce evaporation and decayed leaves and grasses which improve the soil organic matter content and help in soil moisture retention. Also there was high coefficient of variability (CV = 43%) within the land uses as per soil moisture content. This agrees with Yao et al. (2012) who reported that land use was one of the main factors that affected the spatial variations in soil moisture.

Table 3. Mean soil moisture content under Land use types

Land use	Soil Moisture Content (%)
Grassland (GL)	10.39b
Cultivated land (CL)	13.01a
Forested area (FR)	13.53a
SE	0.922
Pr(>F)	0.002
CV (%)	43.00

Effect of sampling depth on soil moisture content (%)

The soil moisture content within the sampled soil depths showed no significant difference ($p=0.495$) between the moisture content (Table 4). This is consistent with Gao and Shao (2012) who observed insignificant variations of soil water at 0–20 cm among various land uses they studied (cropland, shrub land, woodland, and grassland).

Table 4. Effect of sampling depth on soil moisture content

Sampling depth(cm)	Mean
0-15	12.05
15-30	12.58
SE	0.775
Pr(>f)	0.495
CV%	44.28

Effect of temporal variation on soil moisture content

The effect of sampling time (dates) on soil moisture content was presented in Table 5. The result shows that high significant differences exist between the soil moisture content at the different sampling periods. The result showed high moisture content (16.77%) was recorded at the beginning (08/08/2021) and then continue to decline up to the end of August, 2021 (9.52%). The moisture content then increased to 14.55% on 05/09/2021 and decline also to the end of experiment on 31/10/2021 with 5.16%. The sudden increase in soil moisture content after its decline was due to the heavy rainfall experienced on 03/09/2021 and decline to the end of the experiment as no much rainfall was recorded. The increase and decline in soil moisture shows that rainfall has greater influence in soil moisture content, which brings the need for moisture conservation in days without rain.

Table 5. *Effect of sampling date on soil moisture content*

Sampling date	Mean SMC (%)
08-08-21	16.77a
14-08-21	16.42ab
18-08-21	15.23ab
22-08-21	12.49abcd
27-08-21	11.84bcd
31-08-21	9.52cde
05-09-21	14.55ab
19-09-21	13.06abc
03-10-21	12.39abcd
17-10-21	7.99de
31-10-21	5.16e
SE	1.45
Pr(>f)	0.0001
CV%	35.23

Effect rainfall on soil moisture content

There was high significant difference in soil moisture ($p=0.004$) measured after a rainfall event and when there was no rain (Table 6).

Table 6. *Effect of rainfall on soil moisture content*

Rainfall effect	Mean SMC (%)
No rainfall	11.31b
After rainfall	13.51a
SD \pm	5.4
Pr(>f)	0.004
CV, %	43.42

Highest soil moisture content was observed (13.51%) after rainfall and (11.31%) when there was no rainfall. This was in agreement with the report that, in arid land, the soil moisture

content often reached its highest value after a heavier rain, and when the rain had stopped for a couple of days, the soil moisture content decreased sharply due to evapotranspiration, absorption by roots or runoff etc. (Fu et al., 2003) further opined that precipitation was the main factor that influenced the temporal patterns in soil moisture (Yao et al., 2003).

Conclusions

This research work was conducted to evaluate soil moisture content of different land use selected in Federal University Gashua, Bade Local Government Area of Yobe State. The land use types are: grass land, cultivated land and forested area. The study showed that the soils of the study area of Federal University Gashua Bade LGA area are Sandy loam, high in bulk density, low porosity, very low in organic matter content. pH was neutral, EC values, total Nitrogen, organic carbon were very low in the soils, while sodium, available P, Ca, Mg, K and CEC ranged between medium to high concentration. The Land uses have shown greater influence on soil moisture retention, which also vary when measured periodically and consistently also been influenced by rainfall.

References

- Abdullah, A. M., Bose, M. M. and Nuruddin, A. A. (2018). Influence of Monsoon Regime and Microclimate on Soil Respiration in the Tropical Forests. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 12(3), 63-73
- Agada, L. E., Adetola, S. O. and Osita, C. M. (2020). Investigation of the effects of leachate from solid waste dumpsite on groundwater using electrical resistivity method. *Global Scientific Journal* 8(1), 2371-2401.
- Alhassan, I., Gashua, A.G., Dogo, S. and Sani, M. (2018). Physical properties and organic matter content of the soils of Bade in Yobe State, Nigeria. *Int. J. Agric., Environ. & Food Sci.* 2(4),160-163. DOI: 10.31015/jaefs.18027.
- Alhassan, I., Dogo, S., Sani, M. and Hegarty, P. (2020). An Assessment of Some Chemical Properties for Soils in Bade Local Government Area of Yobe State, Nigeria. In: Adesina, J. M., Iwala, O. S., Kekere, O. and Ajayi, A. J. Ajayi E. O. & Idowu-Agida O.O. Book of Proceedings of the 37th Annual Conference of Horticultural Society of Nigeria, Faculty of Agricultural Technology, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State Nigeria. 18th – 22nd November, 2019, 936 – 939.
- Amalu, U. C. (1997). Evaluation of properties of selected soils of Cross River State area and their management for increased cassava yields. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Science* 4(3), 243–249.
- Bationo, A., Buerkert, A. (2001). Soil organic carbon management for sustainable land use in Sudano-Sahelian West Africa. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 61, 131–142.
- Brady, N.C., Weil, R. R. (2013). *The Nature and Properties of Soils*. 12th Ed. Printice-Hall Inc., New Jersey, USA. 785 p.
- Biro, K., Pradhan, B., Buchroithner, M. and Makeschin, F. (2013). Land Use/Land Cover Change Analysis and its impact on Soil Properties in the Northern part of Gadarif Region, Sudan. *Land Degradation and Development*. 24, 90–102.

Brevik, E. C., Cerdà, A., Mataix-Solera, J., Pereg, L., Quinton, J. N., Si, J. and Van Oost, K. (2015). The interdisciplinary nature of SOIL, *SOIL*, 1, 117–129, doi:10.519 /soil-1-117.

Estefan, G., Sommer, R. and Ryan, J. (2013). *Methods of Soil, Plant and Water Analysis: A manual for the West Asia and North Africa region*, 3rd Ed. ICARDA, Beirut, Lebanon. 243 p.

Esu, I. E. (1991). Detailed Soil Survey of NIHORT Farm at Bunkure, Kano State, Nigeria. Institute for Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.

Fu, B. J., Wang, J., Chen, L. D. and Qiu, Y. (2003). The effects of land use on soil moisture variation in the Danangou catchment of the Loess Plateau, China. *Catena*, 54, 197–213.

Gao, L., Shao, M. (2012). Temporal stability of shallow soil water content for three adjacent transects on a hillslope. *Agricultural Water Management*, 110, 41–54. doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2012.03.012

Hamza, M. A., Anderson W. K. (2010). Potential and Limitations of Soil Organic Matter Build-up in Dry Areas. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 5, 2850-2861.

Hao, X., Ball, B.C., Culley, J.L.B., Carter, M.R., Parkin, G.W., Carter, M.R. (Ed.), & Gregorich, EG. (Ed.) (2008). Soil density and porosity. In MR. Carter, & EG. Gregorich (Eds.), *Soil Sampling and Methods of Analysis*. Canadian Society of Soil Science. Advance online publication, 743 - 759.

Hillel, D. (2004). *Introduction to Environmental Soil Physics*. Elsevier Science, Academic Press, USA. 97 p.

Jia, X. X., Shao, M. A., Zhu, Y. J. and Luo, Y. (2017). Soil moisture decline due to afforestation across the Loess Plateau, China. *Journal of Hydrology*, 546, 113–122.

Leh, M., Bajwa, S. and Chaubey, I. (2013). Impact of land use change on erosion risk: an integrated remote sensing, geographic information system and modeling methodology, *Land Degradation Development*, 24, 409–421.

Li, T.C., Shao, M. A., Jia, Y. H., Jia, X. X. and Huang, L. M. (2018). Profile distribution of soil moisture in the gully on the northern Loess Plateau, China. *Catena*, 171, 460–468.

Kumar, R., Shankar, V., & Jat, M. K. (2014). Evaluation of root water uptake models – a review. *ISH Journal of Hydraulic Engineering*, 21(2), 115–124.

Musa, J. J., Adeoye, P. A. (2010). Adaptability of infiltration equations to the soils of the Permanent Site Farm of the Federal University of Technology, Minna, Guinea Savannah zone of Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Technology*, 14 (2), 147-155.

Parras-Alcántara, L., Lozano-García, B. (2014). Conventional tillage versus organic farming in relation to soil organic carbon stock in olive groves in Mediterranean rangelands (southern Spain). *Solid Earth*, 5, 299–311. doi:10.5194/se 5-299-2014.

QldGov (2013). Soil pH. State of Queensland Document on Soil Properties. Available at <https://www.qld.gov.au.environment/land/management/soil/soil-properties/ph-levels>.

Reeuwijk, L.P.V. (1992). *Procedures for soil analysis*. 3rd Ed. International Soil Reference and Information Center (ISRIC), Wageningen, Netherlands 34.

Sharu, M., Yakubu, M. and Tsafe, S. N. A. (2013). Characterization and Classification of Soils on an Agricultural Landscape in Dingyadi District, Sokoto state, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Basic and applied Sciences*, 21(2), 137-147.

Shehu, B. M., Jibrin, J. M. and Samndi, A. M. (2015). Fertility Status of Selected Soils in the Sudan Savanna Biome of Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Soil Science*, 10(2),74-83. doi: 10.3923/ijss.2015.74.83.

Shehu, B. M., Merckx, R., Jibrin, J. M., Kamara, A. Y. and Rurinda, J. (2018). Quantifying Variability in Maize Yield Response to Nutrient Applications in the Northern Nigerian Savanna. *Agronomy*, 8(18),1-23. doi: 10.3390/agronomy8020018.

Seneviratne, S. I., Corti, T. and Davin, E. L. (2010). Investigating soil moisture climate interactions in a changing climate: A review. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 99, 125–161.

Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research [STAR] (2013) Version: 2.0.1. International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). <http://bbi.irri.org>

Yao, S., Zhang, T., Liu, X. and Ma, Y. (2012). Feature of soil saturated hydraulic conductivity in various lands of Horqin Sandy Land. *Journal of Arid Land Resources and Environment*, 26, 123–126.

Ziadat, F. M., Taimeh, A. Y. (2013). Effect of rainfall intensity, slope, land use and antecedent soil moisture on soil erosion in an Arid Environment. *Land Degradation*, 24, 409–421.